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Atmospheric flow simulation strategies to assess turbulent wind conditions for safe drone operations in urban environments

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ABSTRACT

As the technology of small aircraft systems continues to improve and the number of their possible applications grows, they are likely to be used more frequently in urban environments soon. Such environments are especially dangerous due to their high population and structural density in combination with challenging atmospheric conditions. Particularly the local wind field with its often unknown wind shear and turbulence characteristics endangers manned and unmanned aerial vehicles. Therefore, knowledge of the local turbulent wind is essential to ensure safety for the aircraft and the people onboard as well as on ground and should thus be incorporated in mission planning. This study presents a framework of how atmospheric flow analyses can contribute to safe drone operations in urban environments. High-resolution simulations are carried out, utilizing the large-eddy simulation model PALM, which can resolve turbulent flow and building structures down to the meter scale. Our results highlight the advantages and the necessity of using turbulence-resolving models to reasonably arrange a future drone operation network within cities. Because large-eddy simulations of urban environments are still computationally expensive, a meteorological data base for each urban setup should be established to obtain the relevant wind information for mission planning.

1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation

Flying small vehicles in city environments, like package delivery drones or larger-scale urban air taxis, requires good knowledge of local meteorological conditions, especially the turbulent wind field. To ensure safety for the vehicles as well as for people onboard and on the ground, operations need to be conducted in suitable conditions within the design boundaries of the vehicle. Due to their small inertia, low flight altitude, and low flight speed, drones are much more vulnerable to small-scale atmospheric turbulence and wind shear than larger commercial passenger aircraft (Abdulrahim et al., 2010; Lissaman, 2009; Pisano and Lawrence, 2009). During mission planning precise forecasting of the weather is required to evaluate the feasibility

of a mission (i.e., if a service can be offered or not). To avoid hazardous conditions, detailed meteorological analyses should be incorporated in the planning and implementation phase of drone operation scenarios. This will also help to identify suitable landing and departure spots and safe routes. The research presented in this paper proposes a prototype system of meteorological support for urban air mobility (UAM) services and, in particular, for the selection process of vertiports.

Setting up a sustainable ecosystem for UAM requires planning of resources and infrastructure in the area of interest. A network of hubs and supporting services need to be established in order to meet the different business cases and create an efficient operation network. Service availability is one of the most important objective in the provision and operation of a successful UAM program (Gao et al., 2021). Placing the expensive infrastructure at suitable spots that enable operations in almost all weather conditions is essential for an

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Nomenclature

Latin and Greek symbols

d	direction of the geostrophic wind, °
h	boundary layer height, m
I	turbulence intensity, dimensionless
t	total simulation time, h
u	wind velocity in x -direction, m s^{-1}
v	wind velocity in y -direction, m s^{-1}
v_d	magnitude of the mean horizontal wind vector, m s^{-1}
v_g	magnitude of the geostrophic wind, m s^{-1}
v_h	magnitude of the horizontal wind vector, m s^{-1}
\vec{v}_h	horizontal wind vector, m s^{-1}
v_*	characteristic velocity scale, m s^{-1}
w	wind velocity in z -direction, m s^{-1}
x, y, z	Cartesian coordinates, m
θ	potential temperature, K
ν	kinematic viscosity, $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
τ	large-eddy turnover time, s

Operators

$\langle \Psi \rangle$	horizontal average
$\overline{\Psi}$	temporal average
$\bar{\Psi}$	mean value
Ψ'	turbulent quantity

economic drone operation system. The turbulent wind conditions have the greatest impact on the drones (Ranquist et al., 2017), especially in the sensitive phases of hover, the transition to wing-borne flight, or the vertical take-off and landing. Thus, vertiports and related departure and arrival corridors need to be established intelligently, knowing the respective wind conditions and their variation when being placed close to turbulence inducing obstacles.

Weather elements like rain, visibility, and storms are large-scale meteorological phenomena that typically affect the whole airspace in the same way so that critical events generally require to completely interrupt flight operations or to apply restrictions to all flight corridors in the same way. Decisions can be based on publicly available weather prediction or nowcasting products. We will focus here on those weather elements that strongly depend on the local environment, namely the wind conditions (mean wind as well as turbulence), which may vary from corridor to corridor. Even within the same corridor conditions may change within distances of 10 m or less, depending on the local building configuration (Gronemeier et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2008).

Turbulence-resolving numerical models, also called large-eddy simulation (LES) models, are state-of-the-art tools to provide the required high-resolution wind field data (Ferziger and Perić, 2002; Sagaut, 2006). In the following, we will explore how these models can be used to enable safe drone operations in urban environments. At the beginning, a summary about the state of the art of how the weather and especially the turbulent wind field is incorporated in the research about small aerial vehicles as well as an introduction of existing turbulent wind criteria in aviation is given. After that, we will present the applied methodology for simulating and assessing the turbulent wind field in Section 2. Simulation results will be discussed in Section 3 with a focus on the practical applicability of the LES methodology for evaluating drone operation scenarios. Section 4 will conclude our study. The raw data, including model steering files as well as analysis and plot scripts are accessible online (Giersch et al., 2022).

1.2. State of the art

Ranquist et al. (2017) provide a classified overview of the weather hazards that may appear during flights of small unmanned aircraft systems (sUASs). They state that turbulent winds play the largest role in aviation weather accidents, which is true for both sUASs and larger manned aircraft. sUASs in cities are particularly vulnerable to such accidents due to the increased, building induced turbulence and wind shear as well as the high population and structure density. At the same time, possible applications of sUASs in urban environments are great. This includes, for example, law enforcement (Murphy and Cycon, 1999), food delivery services (Li et al., 2020), or disaster management (de Oliveira Silva et al., 2017). Therefore, more and more research starts to focus on the questions how turbulent winds affect sUASs in general and how they can be safely controlled in complex terrain under challenging wind conditions. da Costa Siqueira (2017) analyzed trajectory tracking performance of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) considering different wind phenomena and highlighted how constant wind with turbulence, wind gusts and wind shear pose specific challenges in terms of the design of trajectory control mechanisms. Lissaman (2009) focused on the bank response of flight vehicles to atmospheric turbulence as a function of their wingspan. Especially small aircraft with wingspans of about 1 ft or less are very susceptible to lateral disturbances. Both studies, however, modeled the atmospheric turbulence synthetically by the well-known von Kármán and Dryden wind turbulence models (see e.g., Etkin, 1981; Frost et al., 1982). As these models include many assumptions (e.g., randomness, homogeneity, or isotropy), they are not able to capture the heterogeneous, anisotropic, partly coherent, and nonsteady turbulence in urban settings realistically. Instead, computational fluid dynamics (CFD), which also includes the LES technique, is able to do this, which is why it is used more often now in UAV related flow studies. Paz et al. (2020, 2021) employed CFD simulations to model the flow generated by propellers of a quadcopter UAV and studied aerodynamic effects on flight stability in the proximity of walls and the ground, whereas Mohamed et al. (2015) focused on building-induced updraft regions by using a derivative of the Detached-Eddy Simulation approach to enhance the range and endurance of micro aerial vehicles. Raza (2015) investigated the position control of a quadrotor UAV under diverse representative wind conditions in an urban environment by using LES. A similar study presents a method for examining the effects of urban wake fields on the flight performance of an autonomous quadrotor UAV (Sutherland, 2015). Because LES is computationally expensive, Vuppala and Kara (2021) developed a time efficient, machine learning method to generate realistic wind data for guaranteeing safe operations of sUASs in urban settings, which is able to predict future flow fields based on available LES data. However, it remains unclear if and how reliable their non-intrusive reduced order modeling framework can handle different complex building configurations. In addition, Raza (2015), Sutherland (2015) and Vuppala and Kara (2021) focused only on a single, square building and did not consider the flow for a real urban environment. Variable temperature stratifications were not simulated either although additional turbulence is generated by buoyancy forces during unstable stratification (typical daytime condition) beside the turbulence generated by wind shear (Stull, 1988). According to Sytsma (Sytsma, 2013), there is still a knowledge gap regarding multiple aspects of how turbulent winds affect sUASs which requires further study before they can be effectively used as engineered systems.

In addition to the basic research presented above, operationally orientated methods for a regional quantification of the weather-related flight risk has been developed for UAVs. Lundby et al. (2019) created a framework based on historical weather data and four different types of UAVs, which is capable of providing a weather analysis report to a remote supervisor or to an autonomous decision-making software. Their approach results in a go or no-go output for the planned trajectory. Roseman and Argrow (2020) developed a model that quantifies the

weather hazard risk for sUAS operations in rural to urban environments using weather forecast, population density, structure density, and sUAS data. They finally assess the flight danger by a matrix, which quantifies the risk as acceptable (low), acceptable with mitigation (medium), or unacceptable (high). All risk models have in common that their accuracy depends on the availability of weather information, which they extract from weather prediction models, and flight envelopes, including weather limitation data of the sUASs. Weather prediction models usually work with resolutions well above 1 km and are not suitable to comprehensively evaluate drone operations within cities, where the wind situation can significantly vary even within the same city district. [Roseman and Argrow \(2020\)](#) address this topic in their introduction and state that “sUAS operations in urban environments will likely require data from high-resolution LES simulations to capture the wind and turbulence details necessary for estimating risk”. This becomes even more apparent if considering that most sUAS operations last less than 1 h and span only a distance of about 1 km ([Roseman et al., 2019](#)). The poor availability of weather limitation data for the sUASs is another constraint. [Roseman et al. \(2019\)](#) stress this point in their list about future meteorological and aerospace research areas in the sUAS industry: “Commercial and hobby drones need to be thoroughly tested to quantify their limitations regarding different weather phenomena. Most drones that are purchased only give basic information about weather limitations. They do not give maximum allowable turbulence, maximum or minimum temperature, whether or not they can withstand flying through precipitation, etc”. However, to decide if a sUAS can safely operate within a turbulent wind field or not, reasonable thresholds need to be defined as soon as possible.

Wind and turbulence criteria that shall guarantee safe flights have mostly been developed for larger passenger planes only, focusing on the takeoff and landing phase. For example, manufactures provide information regarding crosswind capabilities of their aircraft, which they must demonstrate during the certification process dictated by the FAA or EASA ([van Es, 2006](#); [Krüs, 2016](#)). Tailwind limits are also provided by manufactures ([van Es and Karwal, 2001](#)). Beside these absolute wind limits, also thresholds for the maximum allowed velocity change/wind shear exist. The so-called “7-knots criterion” by the Netherlands Aerospace Centre is often used, which limits the change of the mean cross wind due to wind disturbing structures to 7 kt if a background crosswind of 25 kt is assumed (e.g., [Liu et al., 2010](#); [Chan and Krus, 2016](#)). [Nieuwpoort et al. \(2010\)](#) state that a wind speed deficit change of 7 kt along the aircraft track (headwind change) must take place over a distance of at least 100 m and that a cross-track speed deficit change of 6 kt must take place over the same distance, which corresponds to gradients of 7 kt/50 m and 6 kt/50 m, respectively. The maximum allowed mean wind gradients suggested by Krüs ([Krüs, 2016](#)) are with 2.0 kt/30 m (headwind change) and 2.5 kt/30 m (crosswind change) even more stringent. In addition to the criteria for the mean wind, thresholds related to the turbulence exist that could endanger airliners if exceeded. In the landing phase, root mean square (RMS) values of the velocity fluctuations may not exceed 4 kt to guarantee safe flights ([Nieuwpoort et al., 2010](#)). Also tables that categorize different turbulence levels with the help of the RMS can be applied to restrict flight operations ([Hoh et al., 1982](#)).

Despite the previously mentioned turbulent wind criteria of manned aircraft, there is still a lag of well tested and generalized thresholds in aviation. The generalization itself is already a difficult task. For example, different aircraft, flight phases or runway conditions strongly affect the values for which safe flight operations can be guaranteed. In other words, wind criteria are only applicable under certain constraints ([Nieuwpoort et al., 2010](#)) and their application in practice features a large scope of interpretation ([van Es, 2006](#); [van Es et al., 2001](#); [van Es, 2012](#)). Therefore, it is not very surprising that wind field thresholds are mostly not known or specified for sUASs - a technology that has been used increasingly since the last decade only (e.g., [Roseman and Argrow, 2020](#)). Authorities like the FAA do not yet consider

turbulent wind velocity thresholds in their operating limitations for sUASs at all. They just highlight the importance of turbulent winds for flight operations, especially in the presence of ground obstructions ([Carty, 2021](#)). Similarly, the Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure in Germany only states that wind thresholds need to be reviewed for the UAS Traffic Management System and to be specified appropriately ([Anon, 2019](#)). Concrete values or ideas how to do that are not given. The Unmanned Aircraft Systems Standardization Collaborative from the American National Standards Institute identified two major gaps regarding UAS operations and weather with a high priority to fill them ([Anon, 2020a](#)). First, weather requirements for flight operations of UAS are mostly missing. For example, certain standards for weather robustness and resiliency must be met by the aircraft but are not known. Second, the weather data standards themselves are problematic. Standards that are currently published fail to provide sufficient resolution (spatial and/or temporal) for certain types of UAS operations, especially in low altitude and boundary layer airspaces. Finally, manufacturers of sUASs only give information about the maximum wind speed resistance in their manuals, while it remains unclear if the mean or the total wind is meant ([Anon, 2020b](#); [Gao et al., 2021](#)).

Despite the difficulties and because of the deficits mentioned above, there is no doubt that the availability of turbulent wind field data is essential for guaranteeing safe flights and for determining drone operation thresholds. This paper addresses the question, how this data can be efficiently obtained and which turbulent wind field quantities may be used to evaluate the safety of an operation.

2. Methodology

The high-resolution state-of-the-art PALM model system 6.0 is used for simulating the turbulent atmospheric flow ([Maronga et al., 2020](#)). PALM has been especially designed for incorporating processes that affect the airflow in urban environments. The model will be described below in more detail. From the simulated Cartesian wind components, we derive specific turbulence measures relevant for drones, which will also be described further below.

Compared to the widespread Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) models that can only predict the mean flow, LES is capable to explicitly simulate the wind field fluctuations due to turbulence, but with the disadvantage of higher simulation complexity, computational costs, and longer simulation times (e.g., [Blocken, 2018](#)). For cases with high spatial resolution and large computational domain sizes, neither LES nor RANS models can run in routine operation on a daily basis. Instead, they can be executed in advance for situations that cover all typical meteorological conditions (e.g., wind speeds, wind directions, atmospheric stratifications) relevant for the specific site. The model data can then be used to generate a data base from which relevant information is extracted based on the actual meteorological conditions as given by in-situ observations or model forecasts. Similar procedures have already been applied, for example, to predict the dispersion of pollutants in case of hazardous incidents ([Patnaik et al., 2008](#)).

Parameter studies with high resolution and for large domains are extremely expensive and sometimes hardly feasible, even on supercomputers. An established way to reduce the computational demand is to use nested model setups (e.g., [Collins et al., 2013](#)), where small domains of about 1 km × 1 km with high spatial resolution (~1 m) are used for areas of special interest (in our case the vertiport surroundings), while the total and much larger simulated domain of about 10 km × 10 km (in our case the complete flight corridor of drones) is modeled with coarser resolution (~10 m). The coarser resolution is justified because most parts of the flight corridors are well above the building height level, where the flight operation is not that sensitive to small-scale variations of the wind field so that they do not have to be simulated explicitly. Simultaneously, small-scale vortices in the direct vicinity of a vertiport, which are generated through nearby buildings or the vertiport building itself and which might be of importance

during the departure/arrival phase of the drone, can be captured by the high resolution. We follow this nesting approach in our study, which is particularly suitable here because especially larger cities are environments that show many specific wind field characteristics on different scales. The total domain with coarse spatial resolution is called the parent domain, while the smaller high-resolution domains are called the children or child domains. They are nested into the parent domain and receive their lateral and top boundary conditions from the parent. We use a two-way nesting approach, meaning that a feedback from the child to the parent is taken into account.

2.1. The LES model PALM

For this study, we use the PALM model system 6.0, revision number 4627, which solves the non-hydrostatic, spatially-filtered, incompressible Navier–Stokes equations in Boussinesq-approximated form and an additional transport equation for the potential temperature. The Navier–Stokes equations include the Coriolis force in a rotating frame of reference to account for the turn of the mean wind vector with height that appears within the atmospheric boundary layer. Time stepping is based on a third-order Runge–Kutta scheme (Williamson, 1980); advection is approximated by a fifth-order scheme by Wicker and Skamarock (Wicker and Skamarock, 2002). Subgrid-scale mixing is parameterized based on a 1.5th-order closure after Deardorff (1980). PALM uses the modified version of Moeng and Wyngaard (1988) and Saiki et al. (2000). Prognostic equations are discretized on a staggered Cartesian grid called the Arakawa C-grid (Arakawa and Lamb, 1977), where scalar quantities are defined at the grid volume's center, whereas velocity components are shifted by half the grid spacing in their respective direction so that they are defined at the edge of a grid volume. A Cartesian topography is considered using the mask method, where a grid cell is either 100% fluid or 100% obstacle (Briscolini and Santangelo, 1989). This allows for a precise representation of vertical building walls. Building and surface data in PALM need to be provided via a so-called static driver file in netCDF data format.

The PALM code is open source and available under the GNU public license v3. It is highly optimized and parallelized, and shows high performance and scalability on all state-of-the-art computer architectures.

PALM includes a variety of further options, for example, a cloud physics module, an air chemistry module, a radiation model, or more advanced boundary conditions, including the nesting into weather forecast models. However, we restrict ourselves here to mention only those features that are used for this study.

LES models in general provide spatially-filtered quantities in their model output. The instantaneous, filtered quantities can be interpreted as a composition of a mean value and the resolved-scale turbulent fluctuation

$$\Psi = \bar{\Psi} + \Psi', \quad (1)$$

where Ψ is the instantaneous value as directly calculated by the model. The tilde denotes any kind of mean and the prime describes the resolved-scale turbulent fluctuation. In fluid dynamics, Eq. (1) is often described as the Reynolds decomposition. The filtering is explicitly reached by applying an analytic filter to the model equations or implicitly by the discretization. PALM uses the spatial scale separation approach after Schumann (Schumann, 1975), where the governing equations are averaged over discrete Cartesian grid volumes. The unresolved turbulence and its influence on the flow solution (mostly negligible, unless close to surfaces) is only parameterized and provided by the so-called subgrid-scale model. To calculate the resolved-scale turbulent contribution Ψ' , it is necessary to subtract a reference value, which represents the mean, from the flow solution (see Eq. (1)). Different ways of how to define and calculate the mean are discussed in the next section.

2.2. Measures for assessing the safety of drone operations

LES allows for calculating almost any statistical data, from the mean wind field up to turbulence spectra or higher order statistical turbulence quantities like the turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) dissipation. Before carrying out any calculations, the first step is to identify those parameters that the drones are sensitive to. However, as discussed in Section 1.2, such measures and threshold values, above which drones cannot be safely operated, are still uncertain or even not known. For this reason, we focus here on general measures, which describe the mean and turbulent state of flow fields and which have already been applied for commercial aircraft or in the field of wind energy (e.g., Chivae, 2014; Hoh et al., 1982). A practical application of the specific measure requires to clarify in advance if the available computational resources allow for a calculation. The demand of such resources strongly depends on the domain size for which the measure needs to be calculated but also on the measure itself. For large number of grid points problems may appear, for example, with respect to the memory, disk space, or slow I/O. An efficient post-processing of time-dependent data is often impossible for the whole model domain due to the huge amount of data that need to be processed. Therefore, the data output from LES must always be carefully tuned to the actual needs.

The magnitude of the horizontal wind vector

$$v_h = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} \quad (2)$$

is one of the most basic measures to characterize the wind conditions. u and v are the first and second velocity component, pointing along the Cartesian coordinates x and y , respectively. Even though the horizontal wind does not quantify the turbulence, high turbulence levels are often associated with high wind speeds. If the mean horizontal flow is regarded, v_h is often analyzed as a temporally and horizontally averaged quantity

$$\langle \bar{v}_h \rangle = \langle \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} \rangle, \quad (3)$$

where the overbar and the angular brackets indicate a temporal and horizontal average, respectively. A common mistake related to the horizontal wind velocity is to confuse it with the absolute value of the mean horizontal wind vector defined as

$$v_d = | \langle \bar{v}_h \rangle | = \sqrt{\langle \bar{u} \rangle^2 + \langle \bar{v} \rangle^2}. \quad (4)$$

For example, if there is no preferred horizontal wind direction, like in a pure convective situation, the mean horizontal wind vector v_d would amount to zero, while the mean horizontal wind velocity $\langle \bar{v}_h \rangle$ would be greater than zero. v_d can be interpreted as the magnitude of the spatial displacement that the fluid experiences on average. Although $\langle \bar{v}_h \rangle$ and v_d are often used to describe the general flow conditions, their meaningfulness is limited, especially in heterogeneous terrain like urban environments. This is true for every horizontally averaged quantity, which is why the following focus is on locally defined measures that take into account the variety of an urban environment.

The magnitude of the mean vertical wind $\langle \bar{w} \rangle$ is not considered as relevant because it is typically very small (a few cm s^{-1}). However, the local, time-averaged vertical wind \bar{w} can, indeed, be large in urban environments, for example, if the air must constantly overflow a building. The instantaneous vertical wind and its time variability can also be very large in case of an unstably stratified atmosphere even if the mean vertical wind is negligible. A local measure that combines all mean velocity components is the mean kinetic energy (MKE) defined as

$$\text{MKE} = \frac{1}{2} (\bar{u}^2 + \bar{v}^2 + \bar{w}^2). \quad (5)$$

The strength of turbulence is often given by the temporally averaged variances of the horizontal (u'^2 , v'^2) and vertical wind (w'^2). They quantify the mean wind “bumpiness” or “gustiness” felt by a vehicle flying through the flow. As explained in Section 2.1, the prime denotes

a turbulent quantity, which is defined as the deviation from a reference (mean) value. In LES, the horizontal average is often used as a reference value. This, however, necessitates horizontal homogeneity of the turbulence statistics. Variances can then be easily calculated online during each time step of the simulation because all required data reside in the computer's memory, for example,

$$u'^2 = (u - \langle u \rangle)^2. \quad (6)$$

To get the temporally averaged variances $\overline{u'^2}$, $\overline{v'^2}$, and $\overline{w'^2}$, instantaneous values are added up during the simulation and the sum is stored. In the end, this sum is divided by the number of time steps within the predefined averaging interval. This approach fails for heterogeneous conditions because the horizontal mean is not necessarily representative for the local environment somewhere in the simulated domain. Instead, the temporally averaged value for each discrete location can be used as reference but it is not yet known during a model time step. The use of

$$\overline{u'^2} = \overline{(u - \bar{u})^2} \quad (7)$$

would require the storage of all instantaneous 3D fields of the u-component within the selected averaging interval. Only after the simulation (or the averaging interval), variances can be determined through first, calculating the temporal average and, second, subtracting this average from the instantaneous values that has been stored. Afterwards, the result of the subtraction is summed up and divided by the number of time steps (or stored 3D fields) to get the temporally averaged variances. For a large number of grid points or large averaging periods, this approach quickly becomes impractical, if not impossible. By applying the Reynolds decomposition and using the Reynolds averaging rules, local variances can be calculated with much less resources as follows (the same for v and w)

$$\overline{u^2} = \overline{(\bar{u} + u')^2} = \bar{u}^2 + \overline{u'^2}, \quad (8)$$

$$\Rightarrow \overline{u'^2} = \overline{u^2} - \bar{u}^2. \quad (9)$$

The values for $\overline{u^2}$ and \bar{u}^2 are directly obtained during the simulation and no storage of time-dependent 3D data is necessary. This procedure is known as the temporal eddy-covariance method, whereas Eq. (6) is often called the spatial eddy-covariance method.

Similar to the MKE, the TKE combines all three wind components but with respect to the fluctuations and not the mean:

$$\text{TKE} = \frac{1}{2} (\overline{u'^2} + \overline{v'^2} + \overline{w'^2}). \quad (10)$$

The "gustiness" of the flow and, therefore, the TKE highly depends on the eddy size. As the energy density decreases with decreasing eddy size, a flying vehicle experiences many small bumps when flying through small eddies, while intense bumps connected to larger eddies are quite rare events, which may happen during the transition from an updraft to a downdraft, for example.

Another key parameter to quantify the level of turbulence is the mean dissipation rate of TKE ϵ , which generally increases as the turbulence level increases and which has already been applied in aviation (e.g., Sarpkaya, 2000, Sharman et al., 2014). It describes how much TKE is dissipated into heat when the turbulent scales are small enough for viscous dissipation to be effective and it is directly linked to the production of TKE at large turbulent scales. Assuming stationary turbulence, dissipation equals production, which is why the dissipation rate is a direct measure for the strength of turbulence. The local dissipation rate can be derived from the turbulent velocity gradients as

$$\epsilon = \frac{\nu}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u'_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u'_j}{\partial x_i} \right)^2. \quad (11)$$

The subscripts $i, j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ denote the different velocity components u , v , and w . Under homogeneous conditions, the turbulent velocity can again be determined during the simulation by using the horizontal

average as in Eq. (6). A heterogeneous terrain, however, requires the calculation of the temporal average as a reference value ($u'_i = u_i - \bar{u}_i$) and therefore the output of time series at all model grid points for which ϵ shall be known. Time series data of the total velocities enable the calculation of energy spectra from which the turbulent dissipation rate can also be derived (instead of directly using Eq. (11)). In case of large domains, the output data amount easily exceed hundreds of terabytes, which is not feasible even on very big computer systems. The huge amount of data together with the complexity of the calculation make the dissipation rate of TKE an impractical measure for heterogeneous conditions, especially if conclusions for the whole simulation domain shall be derived with high spatial resolution. Different calculation techniques of ϵ are summarized in Wang et al. (2021).

The gust factor and turbulence intensity provide relative measures for the turbulence level. The gust factor is defined as the ratio of the maximum gust speed to the mean wind speed. The maximum gust speed is often defined as the highest wind peak that results from the application of a moving time average of about 2 s to the original wind data. For the mean wind speed, 10-minute segments of wind speed data are typically taken (Paulsen and Schroeder, 2005). The definition of the turbulence intensity differs from author to author and depends on the field of application. It can be defined for each component as the ratio of the RMS of the turbulent velocity fluctuation, also called standard deviation, and the local mean flow velocity (e.g., Koziol, 2013)

$$I_x = \frac{\sqrt{\overline{u'^2}}}{\bar{u}}, \quad (12)$$

$$I_y = \frac{\sqrt{\overline{v'^2}}}{\bar{v}}, \quad (13)$$

$$I_z = \frac{\sqrt{\overline{w'^2}}}{\bar{w}}, \quad (14)$$

or for the whole wind vector (e.g., Russo and Basse, 2016)

$$I = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{3}(\overline{u'^2} + \overline{v'^2} + \overline{w'^2})}}{|\bar{\vec{v}}|} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{3}(\overline{u'^2} + \overline{v'^2} + \overline{w'^2})}}{\sqrt{\bar{u}^2 + \bar{v}^2 + \bar{w}^2}}. \quad (15)$$

One feature of the turbulence intensity is its asymptotic behavior as the wind speed increases. Several numerical, theoretical and practical studies showed that I depends only little on the mean wind speed as soon as an asymptotic value of about 10 m s^{-1} is reached (e.g., Rodrigues et al., 2010; Emeis, 2014). Under this assumption, I needs to be calculated only once from a simulation with an arbitrary high mean wind speed to determine the turbulent velocity variances for any other observed wind speed higher than the asymptotic value. However, this procedure is only valid for horizontally homogeneous surfaces with constant surface roughness. Additionally, the independence of I on the mean wind is violated for low wind speeds and must still be investigated for complex terrain like urban environments.

Finally, wind gusts can be identified in the simulated flow fields to evaluate the safety of flights. The gust response analysis and evaluation is still an up-to-date topic in modern flight vehicle design and daily air traffic (Hashemi et al., 2018; van Es, 2012). One of the most critical points in gust identification and analysis is the definition of a gust (e.g., Knigge and Raasch, 2016). Especially in the practical design and certification process of aircraft, discrete models are still mostly applied, although they simplify and idealize real atmospheric gusts significantly (Wu et al., 2019). Numerical simulations like LES provide a much more realistic way to simulate and define gusts. A generic and novel gust definition and detection method was recently developed by Knoop et al. (2019). The method uses wavelet-analysis to detect amplitudes and their respective periods that are contained within a wind velocity signal at a given time. In this way, a specific amplitude can be picked and it can be determined how often this amplitude

appears or is exceeded within a chosen period. However, to apply this method, it is necessary to know which gust structures (amplitude and period) are harmful to the regarded flight object but this information is currently unknown for most, if not all, sUASs. Another problem might be the provision of sufficiently long time series of wind velocities for every grid point, where the gust detection method shall be applied. For large domains, disk space problems will easily occur.

The above list of general measures describing the mean and turbulent state of the flow is not complete. Other measures like the vorticity, skewness, third-order moments or spectra might be interesting for drone applications in urban environments as well. To narrow down the available measures to the relevant ones, it will be essential in the future to identify the meteorological parameters that are suitable to indicate the sensitivity of sUASs with respect to the turbulent wind field. We will focus here on the mean wind, variances, the TKE, and some instantaneous velocity signals mainly because of their simple, cost-efficient, and resource-friendly calculation.

In a next step, the numerical setups used for generating the required turbulent wind field data are introduced. They should be regarded as a first step toward a realistic simulation of urban setups. Based on the flow solution that arises from these setups, the following sections show how drone-related wind field analyses can be performed with minimized resource requirements.

2.3. Numerical setups

We chose Kowloon Peninsula in Hong Kong as the target region for our simulations, mainly because of its complex, densely populated building setup, and because studies for this area were already performed in the past (e.g., Gronemeier et al., 2017) so that building data with a high resolution of 2 m is available (see Fig. 1). For simplicity, the natural terrain is not considered because it is mostly flat. In addition, surfaces are treated equally regardless of whether they are water, asphalt, vegetation or building surfaces. The main simulation parameters are listed in Table 1 and are explained below. The simulation name is selected as follows: The first part describes the atmospheric stratification (“N” for neutral, “C” for convective). If a lower-case letter follows, it distinguishes between child (“c1” for child 1 and “c2” for child 2) and parent domain (“p”). Simultaneously, it indicates whether the nesting technique is applied or not. Remember that the nested simulation is a single simulation that consists of several model instances (depending on the number of child domains), which run in parallel to each other with the same time step and which continuously communicate during the simulation, for example, if boundary conditions need to be exchanged. For non-nested runs, the number in the name describes the magnitude of the geostrophic wind v_g followed by a lower-case letter, indicating the geostrophic wind direction (“e” for east, “sw” for southwest). The endings e^- and e^+ denote a modification of $\pm 5^\circ$ compared to the easterly wind direction. In total, two nested simulations are performed, which we will introduce first. They mainly differ in their atmospheric stratification and the number of child domains.

The parent of the convective case (Cp) contains two child simulation domains for more detailed analyses, one in the north (Cc1) and one in the south (Cc2). The neutral case (Np) only considers one child (Nc1) to save some computing costs. The grid spacings are a compromise between resolution and computing costs (see also Section 3.4). Note, we do not intend to resolve the turbulent scales the drones are most sensitive to. This would probably require grid spacings of about 0.5 m, depending on the type of drone. Our focus is on the general evaluation of the urban flow for which a resolution of 2 m is sufficient (e.g., Hertwig et al., 2017). The children include four different vertiports, which are the focus of our investigations. The three vertiports in the northernmost domain (vertiport 1 to 3, starting with the one in the north) were selected based on the following two requirements: First, the location should be at intermediate heights between the street level and the highest building roofs as well as free of obstructions. Second, the

vertiport’s area should be large enough to allow for comfortable ground operations. The single vertiport in the southernmost domain (vertiport 4) already exists in reality and is called the West Kowloon Heliport located at the roof top of The Peninsula - a five star luxury hotel. The total simulation time t depends on the considered temperature stratification. The reason for this is explained in Section 3. A differentiation between a neutrally and unstably stratified boundary layer is essential here. Under neutral conditions, the turbulent flow is only shear-driven, whereas under unstable conditions turbulence is significantly generated by buoyancy forces. This has a great impact on the city’s wind field characteristics (e.g., Gronemeier et al., 2017). From a domain height of 600 m (well above the city), vertical grid stretching is applied to save computing time.

PALM is able to handle very complex meteorological and boundary conditions like daily cycles or the detailed surface structure of building walls, including their heat capacity (Maronga et al., 2020). However, for this study we restrict ourselves to generic and stationary meteorological setups as well as to simplified building walls, which are only characterized by their surface roughness. We use a constant roughness length of 0.1 m for all surfaces, which is in agreement with former studies (Gronemeier et al., 2017, 2021). For model setups with unstable temperature stratification, a typical kinematic sensible surface heat flux $w\theta$ of 0.2 K m s^{-1} (approximately 235 W m^{-2}) is prescribed for all horizontal surfaces (Cui and Chui, 2021). Vertical building walls do not release any heat, which roughly corresponds to a situation with a sun zenith angle of 0° . To prevent a constant increase in boundary layer height due to the continuous heat input, large-scale subsidence is enabled. This emulates a typical situation under high pressure conditions. Above 1400 m, a so-called Rayleigh damping or sponge layer is applied. It effectively damps gravity waves caused by boundary layer convection, which may propagate vertically in the inversion layer and would be reflected at the top boundary. In addition to the surface heat flux, the flow is driven by a purely easterly geostrophic wind of 3 m s^{-1} . For Np and Nc1, this background wind is the only driving force for the flow.

The selection of the wind magnitude and direction is based on climate observations from the Hong Kong Observatory (see <https://www.hko.gov.hk/en/cis/climat.htm>). In total, four stations (Kings Park, Star Ferry, Yau Yat Chuen, and Cheung Sha Wan) has been analyzed. Their climate data show that daily mean wind speed values between 2 and 4 m s^{-1} are representative for Kowloon Peninsula. From September to April, the prevailing wind direction is from the east (90°). From May to August it mostly varies between southeast (135°) and southwest (225°). It is probable that this mean meteorological situation is not critical for drone operations at all. However, because there are currently no specific wind/turbulence thresholds available to define no-fly zones (see Section 1.2), it is not necessary to simulate a potentially critical case with background winds of 10 m s^{-1} or more. It would just increase the computing costs (higher wind speeds require smaller time steps for numerical stability) without any new conclusions. For the feasibility study presented here, we focus on typical wind conditions that may occur in Hong Kong.

The top and bottom boundary of the parent’s model domain are impermeable ($w = 0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). At the bottom, a no-slip Dirichlet boundary condition ($u = v = 0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) is assumed together with a zero gradient condition for the potential temperature in case of surface heating and a constant value ($\theta = 300 \text{ K}$) otherwise. For the top boundary, a Dirichlet condition is employed, where u and v are set to the geostrophic value of 3 and 0 m s^{-1} , respectively. Between a surface (ground as well as building surfaces) and the first computational grid level perpendicular to the surface, a constant flux layer is assumed to calculate the surface shear stresses and scalar fluxes via Monin–Obukhov similarity theory (Monin and Obukhov, 1954). In the horizontal directions of the parent, cyclic boundary conditions are used, meaning that the outflow on one side is used as the inflow on the upstream side of the domain. The use of cyclic boundary conditions is generally justified by the assumption that

Fig. 1. Building height information for the simulation domains. The black squares in a mark the locations of the first and second child in the north and south, respectively. The yellow dots in b and c denote the locations of the vertiports. Areas in dark blue indicate water surfaces. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 1

Summary of simulation parameters. Nested simulations are separated from each other and from the non-nested cases by horizontal lines.

Simulation name	Domain size $L_x \times L_y \times L_z$ (m^3)	Number of grid points	Grid spacing (m)	Atmospheric Stability	v_g ($m s^{-1}$)	d ($^\circ$)	$w\theta$ ($K m s^{-1}$)	t (h)
Np	$6000 \times 9000 \times 2345$	$600 \times 900 \times 102$	10	neutral	3	90	0	65
Nc1	$1040 \times 1040 \times 521$	$520 \times 520 \times 262$	2	neutral	3	90	0	65
Cp	$6000 \times 9000 \times 2345$	$600 \times 900 \times 102$	10	unstable	3	90	0.2	14
Cc1	$1040 \times 1040 \times 521$	$520 \times 520 \times 262$	2	unstable	3	90	0.2	14
Cc2	$1040 \times 1040 \times 521$	$520 \times 520 \times 262$	2	unstable	3	90	0.2	14
N3e	$1024 \times 1024 \times 1885$	$512 \times 512 \times 290$	2	neutral	3	90	0	65
N10e	$1024 \times 1024 \times 1885$	$512 \times 512 \times 290$	2	neutral	10	90	0	65
N3sw	$1024 \times 1024 \times 1885$	$512 \times 512 \times 290$	2	neutral	3	225	0	65
N10sw	$1024 \times 1024 \times 1885$	$512 \times 512 \times 290$	2	neutral	10	225	0	65
C3e	$2048 \times 2048 \times 2201$	$1024 \times 1024 \times 322$	2	unstable	3	90	0.2	14
C10sw	$2048 \times 2048 \times 2201$	$1024 \times 1024 \times 322$	2	unstable	10	225	0.2	14
C3e	$2048 \times 2048 \times 2201$	$1024 \times 1024 \times 322$	2	unstable	3	90	0.2	14
C10sw	$2048 \times 2048 \times 2201$	$1024 \times 1024 \times 322$	2	unstable	10	225	0.2	14
N3e ⁻	$1024 \times 1024 \times 1885$	$512 \times 512 \times 290$	2	neutral	3	95	0	65
N3e ⁺	$1024 \times 1024 \times 1885$	$512 \times 512 \times 290$	2	neutral	3	85	0	65

the flow characteristics in the inner domain far from the boundaries do not depend on the specific kind of lateral boundary conditions. The child domains obtain their lateral and top boundary conditions from the parent solution through interpolation.

The simulations are initialized with height constant velocity profiles (see Fig. 2 left). The horizontal velocities are set to the geostrophic values, while w is initially zero everywhere. The potential temperature

is 300 K in the neutral case (see Fig. 2 right). Under unstable stratification, the potential temperature field is initialized with constant values of 292 K up to 800 m and a capping inversion above with a gradient of $0.006 K m^{-1}$. 292 K corresponds to a surface temperature of about 20 °C if a surface pressure of 1013.25 hPa is assumed.

In addition to the nested cases, ten non-nested simulations of the first child domain (Fig. 1b) are executed to investigate the sensitivity

Fig. 2. Profiles of the magnitude of the horizontally and temporally averaged horizontal wind vector (left) and potential temperature (right) at the end of the simulations Np and Cp together with their initial profiles (parent).

of the results on the wind direction (90° and 225°) and speed (3 and 10 m s^{-1}) as well as the atmospheric stratification in detail (see again Table 1). The neutral setups (N) have a slightly smaller horizontal extent compared to the nested simulations of child 1 (Nc1) due to technical reasons related to the nesting. For the unstable setups (C), the domain size is larger than for N to guarantee the resolution of the largest, turbulent scales with a horizontal extent comparable to the boundary layer depth (about 1 km in this study, see Section 3). They should be captured by the simulation in order to obtain reasonable estimates of the turbulence strength. The larger domain for the unstable case is constructed as a periodic extension of the smaller neutral domain. In this way, an approximate homogeneity of the surface building distribution is preserved. We reject the alternative of directly extending the neutral domain on the complete city map because it would introduce large surface inhomogeneities (see Fig. 1a), which would complicate a direct comparison between the neutral and unstable cases. Additionally, cyclic boundary conditions are applied and vertical grid stretching is used from 450 m, which is well above the highest building (224 m). All other settings regarding boundary conditions or model initialization are the same as for the nested runs. To investigate how small wind direction changes of $\pm 5^\circ$ affect the results, two additional simulations of the neutral non-nested case are performed (N3e⁻ and N3e⁺).

3. Results and discussion

At the beginning of this section, a general overview of specific simulation features and the meteorological situations that are simulated is given. Afterwards, drone-related simulation results are highlighted with a focus on nested simulations, sensitivities regarding wind direction and stratification, and virtual flights - a technique that provides flight measurements along a predefined flight track during the flow simulation. Finally, the computational resources that are necessary for performing the simulations are discussed. Because quantitative conclusions are only of minor importance in our study, we focus on a more qualitative

analysis. Note, wind field analyses around the locations of interest can be carried out in almost any detailedness and complexity, for example, by using all the measures that were mentioned in Section 2.2. However, this study wants to give a general overview about meteorological analyses that might be relevant during the establishment of future drone operation networks in urban environments. A detailed investigation of the example case presented here is therefore not effective.

Fig. 2 indicates vertical profiles of the magnitude of the horizontally and temporally averaged horizontal wind vector v_d and potential temperature $\overline{\theta}$ at the beginning and end of the simulations Np and Cp, respectively. The parent solution can be seen as representative for the overall meteorological conditions in each domain. For getting time-averaged statistics, a temporal average of a period of 10 h in the convective case and 50 h in case of neutral stratification before the respective output time and after the flow is in a stationary state is considered. This state is reached after a spin-up time of 4 h under unstable and 15 h under neutral conditions as time series of different flow quantities, for example, the domain-averaged kinetic energy of the flow, indicate. Convection accelerates the process to a fully developed stationary state due to enhanced vertical mixing. The difference in the averaging time takes into account different large-eddy turnover times $\tau = h/v_*$ that occur under both stability conditions. The parameter h describes the boundary layer height and v_* a characteristic velocity scale for the larger eddies. For neutral conditions, h is taken as the height where the magnitude of the turbulent shear stress $\sqrt{\overline{w'u'^2} + \overline{w'v'^2}}$ is less than 10% of its near-surface maximum value for the first time. The velocity scale v_* corresponds to the near-surface maximum value of $(\overline{w'u'^2} + \overline{w'v'^2})^{0.25}$. In the convective regime, h is defined as the height where the first minimum of the total turbulent heat flux (subgrid scale + resolved scale) relative to the height levels below and above occurs, whereas v_* is equal to Deardorff's vertical velocity scale (see also (Wurps et al., 2020)). With these formula, large-eddy turnover times of about 110 min and 8 min are calculated for the neutral and convective situation. Hence, the above defined averaging

periods contain roughly 27τ and 75τ , respectively. The combination of the required spin-up time and the averaging periods explains the different simulation times mentioned in Section 2.3.

The profiles in Fig. 2 on the left show a vertically more pronounced shear zone if neutral conditions are assumed, whereas the convection causes a well-mixed boundary layer flow except close to the surface and the boundary layer top, which marks the transition between the boundary layer and the free atmosphere — the so-called entrainment zone. Under both conditions, turbulence is produced by wind shear of the mean flow. In the unstable case, turbulence is additionally generated by buoyancy, which enhances the TKE and mixing significantly (see also Section 3.2). The atmospheric boundary layer is characterized by lower displacement velocities v_d if the surface is heated. This is caused by the stable stratification at the top (see Fig. 2 on the right), which decouples the boundary layer from the free atmosphere, leading to a decreased momentum flux from above. The averaged wind direction in the lower part of the atmospheric boundary layer is northeast (see also Fig. 4) with high horizontal velocities over the sea and low velocities on the leeward side of the buildings. The mean wind direction is not directly from east as the employed background wind would suggest because in the northern hemisphere the Coriolis force causes a turn of the geostrophic wind to the left (anti-clockwise).

The potential temperature profiles in Fig. 2 on the right indicate a growing boundary layer height from about 800 m to slightly above 1000 m for NC. However, this growth is restricted to the spin-up phase of the model. In the equilibrium state, h stays constant due to the activated large-scale subsidence. The constant heating causes the surface temperature to increase during the whole simulation. In simulation Np, θ remains at the initial value of 300 K.

The vertical profiles of the mean velocity variances in the parent domain are plotted in Fig. 3. They demonstrate an overall increase in the variances' magnitude if an unstably instead of a neutrally stratified boundary layer is considered although the mean horizontal displacement velocity v_d in the boundary layer is even smaller in the convective case. The strongest horizontal wind fluctuations are simulated in the lower part of the boundary layer (~ 50 m) due to the wind shear generated by the surface roughness and the buildings. Especially these altitudes are probably the most relevant and critical for future drone operations in cities (e.g., Doole et al., 2021). A second maximum is visible within the entrainment zone at the boundary layer top of the convective case. At these heights, the increased turbulence is related to the increased vertical wind shear of the mean wind (see also Fig. 2). Vertical velocity fluctuations show a distinct maximum at a level of 1/3 of the inversion height provoked by the upward and downward accelerating air parcels through the buoyancy force. For drones, stronger variances and therefore stronger wind fluctuations generally mean bumpier and riskier flights. All vertical profiles shown so far agree well with other studies (e.g., Nieuwstadt et al., 1993; Vasaturo et al., 2018).

A further general difference between both stability regimes is the appearance of coherent structures. The unstable case features coherent structures in form of polygonal, cellular flow patterns up to several 100 m height with a horizontal size similar to the boundary layer depth. These patterns become, for example, visible in instantaneous, horizontal cross sections of the vertical velocity. The neutral case reveals more streamwise-oriented, band-like structures. These well-known features are not shown here explicitly but have been frequently discussed in the literature (e.g., Gronemeier et al., 2017; Schmidt and Schumann, 1989; Jayaraman and Brasseur, 1989).

3.1. 3D wind field and TKE in nested simulations

Fig. 4 shows horizontal cross sections of the temporally averaged TKE and streamlines of the mean horizontal wind vector \bar{v}_h for each domain of simulation NC. As this study focuses on evaluating turbulent wind fields around potential vertiports, building height following sections at 5 m above ground are shown. In addition, the street level is

excluded to improve readability. A general overview of the horizontal wind and especially the TKE on Kowloon Peninsula is provided by NCp in Fig. 4a. City districts or even single buildings indicating high turbulence levels can be identified and excluded in the selection process of the sites for the potential vertiports. For example, buildings at exposed locations, where the wind is coming from the sea without hindrance, show strong turbulence (red colors). The mean wind is relatively high at these locations and causes intense shear zones in the vicinity of the buildings, which result in an increased generation of turbulence. The same effect explains the large areas of high TKE values in the north (yellow, orange, and red colors), whereas in the first child domain as well as northwest and south of it, low TKE values (blue and green colors) are dominant in the parent solution. This is further supported by the high-resolution child 1 result (NCc1) in Fig. 4b. The background flow is slowed down significantly and diverted in various directions by the dense building structure. The lower mean wind results in a weaker wind shear and finally in lower TKE. The locations for the potential vertiports are therefore a reasonable selection, at least for the meteorological situation examined here. The solution in the second child (see Fig. 4c) indicates higher horizontal wind velocities and turbulence levels compared to the first one, especially in the west and south near the sea. However, vertiport 4 is located at the leeward side of the building structures about 200 m north of the shore, where the mean wind shear is reduced. Therefore, its TKE level is comparable to the three vertiports in the first child domain.

In assessment studies of weather-related flight risks, local vertical wind profiles for special locations can be consulted, where flight operations are particularly sensitive to turbulent winds, for example, at departure or landing spots. To demonstrate this, local vertical profiles of the temporally averaged wind components above the three vertiports of child 1 are discussed in the following (see Fig. 5). Both horizontal wind components show a similar behavior at the different locations except above the second vertiport (second column) between 50 and 200 m under neutral conditions (blue lines), where the wind magnitude is decreased compared to vertiport 1 and 3. Such a difference is not apparent under unstable stratification (red lines). In addition, surface heating reduces the absolute values of the mean u -component (note the negative scale) but increases the wind fluctuations in x - and y -direction (see the horizontal bars). For the v -component, fluctuations with respect to the mean are significantly larger compared to the u -component because of the applied background wind, which is only in x -direction. This also causes the absolute values of the mean v -component to be mostly lower compared to \bar{u} . Furthermore, vertical profiles of \bar{v} are less affected by the stratification than those of \bar{u} . The mean vertical motion above all vertiports is negligible with respect to the other wind components and therefore not further discussed. More information on how the stratification changes the results is given in Section 3.2, where also the effects of different background winds are addressed.

Beside the analysis of vertical profiles above the vertiports in the child 1 domain, local profiles at the heliport position in child 2 have also been analyzed. As an example, \bar{v} is shown in Fig. 5 and compared with the profile above vertiport 1, 2, and 3 (convective case). The differences between the heliport's \bar{v} -profile and those of the vertiports are much more pronounced compared to the differences among the vertiports 1 to 3 for the convective situation. For example, a vertically larger and stronger shear zone develops directly above the heliport and the absolute \bar{v} -values start to decrease slightly from a height of approximately 250 m. Such a decrease is not apparent in the vertiports' \bar{v} -profiles. These differences arise due to the completely different building structure in both child domains (see Fig. 1) and due to the vertiports' heights. In child 1, the roof tops are between 35 and 50 m, whereas the roof top of the heliport in child 2 is located at around 125 m. The above discussion about the local profiles illustrates the variety of the turbulent wind situation in urban environments induced by buildings and changes in atmospheric stratification. This variety can

Fig. 3. Profiles of the horizontally and temporally averaged variance for each component at the end of the simulations Np and Cp.

Fig. 4. Horizontal cross sections of the temporally averaged TKE and streamlines at 5 m above ground at the end of the simulation NC. The black squares in a mark the locations of the first and second child in the north and south, respectively. The black dots in b and c denote the locations of the vertiports. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Local profiles of the temporally averaged wind components \bar{u} and \bar{v} (row 1 and 2) above the vertiports 1, 2, 3 (from left to right) at the end of the simulations Nc1 and Cc1. At the bottom, local profiles of \bar{v} above the vertiports 1, 2, 3 are compared with the heliport's \bar{v} -profile (child 2, vertiport 4). The bars indicate a difference from the mean of \pm one standard deviation that appear for the instantaneous profiles. Red lines illustrate the convective case, blue lines the neutral case, and orange lines the heliport's profile. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

only be reliably captured with high-resolution LES in order to be able to draw conclusions about individual locations.

Finally, Fig. 6 displays vertical cross sections of the instantaneous vertical velocity and streamlines of $\sqrt{u^2 + w^2}$. For better visualization, the x -axis of the parent domain has been shortened and the z -axis ends at a height of approximately 200 m. Fig. 6 gives an impression of how dynamical the flow moves in and around an urban environment, an information that cannot be derived from time-averaged fields. In the convective situation, strong up- and downdrafts occur, especially above the city (e.g., at $x = 2100$ m or at $x = 3800$ m in the parent domain), that penetrate the whole boundary layer. The vertical movements induced by the surface heating dominate the instantaneous cross sections in every domain, thus reducing the influence of the buildings on the

flow pattern. This observation is in agreement with Gronemeier et al. (2017), who also found out a reduced impact of buildings on the flow field during convective situations compared to neutral stratification. However, at some positions, local wind effects due to the building layout are still visible. On the one hand, thermally induced vertical movements are temporarily intensified by buildings, where the air is forced to flow over them (e.g., at $x = 200$ m in child 2). On the other hand, buildings can cause a flow in the opposite direction of the applied geostrophic wind. In the upper layers, the air is horizontally moving from east to west (right to left) most of the times, whereas close to the ground movements from west to east are also apparent (e.g., at the lower left corner in the parent and child 2 domain). All these local features might be relevant for drone operations.

Fig. 6. Vertical cross sections of the instantaneous vertical velocity and streamlines at $y = 4505$ m (a), $y = 461$ m (b), and $y = 505$ m (c) at the end of the simulation NC. Buildings are displayed in black. The green dots in b and c denote the locations of the vertiports.

3.2. Sensitivity study on wind and stratification

The magnitude of the background wind, its direction, and the atmospheric stratification are three of the most important meteorological parameters that affect the flow pattern in urban environments (e.g., Gronemeier et al., 2017; Claus et al., 2012; Zajic et al., 2011; Mittal et al., 2018). Therefore, every study that wants to assess the flight risk from turbulent wind fields must take variations of these parameters and their consequences for the air flow into account. As described in Section 2.3, we limit the sensitivity study regarding the prescribed geostrophic wind and stratification to ten non-nested simulations of the child 1 domain. Further simulations or parameter studies for the more realistic nested cases are computationally too expensive and also not necessary for the generalized assessment study presented here.

One main result is that the TKE generally increases with increasing background wind speed (from 3 to 10 m s^{-1}) and when the stratification changes from neutral to unstable. In fact, this is not surprising. Other studies already suggest these relationships (e.g., Mahrt et al., 2015). In addition, higher turbulence in case of higher wind speeds and daytime convection fits to our daily experience, especially in the presence of obstacles near the ground. Also from a theoretical point of view, higher wind speeds and unstable stratification must result in higher turbulence levels. First, larger background winds produce more intense shear zones. This shear appears as a positive term in the budget equation for the TKE (mechanical production of turbulence). Second, buoyancy created by the unstable stratification also acts as a positive contribution in the budget equation. The increased TKE causes the flights to be more unstable, which may require larger distances between flight objects or other obstacles and reduces the capacity of the flight corridors.

For each given stability case and magnitude of the geostrophic wind, vertical profiles of v_d and the horizontally and temporally averaged

TKE demonstrate an overall increase in the wind speed and a decrease in TKE below 750 m as the direction of the geostrophic wind changes from east to south-west (not shown). This is a consequence of the varying building shapes and sizes the prevailing wind is encountering in streamwise direction. Physically, it can be described by the form drag of the buildings, which varies when the wind direction changes. Higher form drags decrease the wind speed, whereas the turbulence increases behind the obstacles. Therefore, it can be concluded that a south-westerly geostrophic wind results in a lower domain-averaged form drag, which may entail more stable flight paths.

The differences of the TKE and the wind speed due to the change in wind direction are more pronounced for the neutral than the unstable cases, which can also be derived from the vertical profiles mentioned in the previous paragraph. But also horizontal cross sections of the mean wind, showing the local situation, reveal this finding. Fig. 7 indicates the local difference of the magnitude of the temporally averaged horizontal wind vector between the two wind sectors for both simulated geostrophic wind velocities and stratifications at the end of the simulation. As in Fig. 4, building height following sections at 5 m above ground are displayed, neglecting the surface level. The results show that the differences are more pronounced in the neutral case (overall darker colors in Fig. 7a, b compared to Fig. 7c, d), which is a direct consequence of the increased mixing and reduced dynamic effects of the buildings on the flow in the convective regime (Gronemeier et al., 2017). Note, the color scale changes from low wind speeds (Fig. 7a, c) to high wind speeds (Fig. 7b, d). The increased mixing becomes obvious when analyzing the vertical profiles of the velocity variances - a possibility for quantifying the strength of the mixing. Similar to Fig. 3, higher values are simulated for each component in the unstably stratified atmosphere due to the overturning convective cells close to the surface and the more pronounced up- and downward motions, which especially occur at a level of about 1/3 of the boundary

Fig. 7. Differences of the absolute values of the temporally averaged horizontal wind vectors between the south-westerly (225°) and easterly (90°) geostrophic wind direction at 5 m above ground at the end of the simulation. At the top, results for the neutral setups (N) are displayed, whereas the second row shows the results for the convective cases (C), each with 3 and 10 m s^{-1} geostrophic wind. The green dots mark the potential vertiports. Note that the color scale changes between the two wind speed regimes. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

layer height. Furthermore, the influence of the form drag on the flow is reduced in the unstable situation by strong vertical motions. This also causes smaller differences between the two wind sectors in the unstable simulations (Fig. 7c, d) compared to the neutral simulations (Fig. 7a, b). In addition, Fig. 7 shows a similar amount of locations with an increase and decrease in the wind speed (portion of red colors/positive values is similar to the blue/negative ones), which reveals the horizontal heterogeneity of the results and stresses the need for a detailed analysis of the local situation with respect to drone operations. The absolute magnitude of the differences is higher for a background wind of 10 m s^{-1} . However, changes of the geostrophic wind velocity do not alter the qualitative result significantly (compare Fig. 7a with b and c with d). In the particular case of the three potential vertiports (green dots), wind speed variations between the two investigated wind sectors are small (less than 10% of the geostrophic value), which is true for both stratifications and geostrophic wind magnitudes. However, depending on the regarded location, these wind speed variations can become quite large (20–30% of the geostrophic value).

The possible dependency of the turbulent wind fields on the wind direction proves that it is imperative to carry out studies for all the wind directions that are relevant in the safety analysis of the drone operation scenario. Depending on the wind climatology, it might be required to

study all wind directions from 0 to 360° . For practical purposes, these studies must be finished before the actual operation starts and results must be integrated into a data base, which finally provides the relevant wind information, depending on the actual meteorological conditions at the beginning and during the flights (see also Section 2). To minimize the need for computing resources, it is essential to know in which step size the relevant wind directions must be examined. This strongly depends on the sensitivity of the results regarding wind direction changes. Unfortunately, the findings described above show that it is not possible to draw any general conclusions from the results of one wind situation for another one. Additionally, it is challenging to determine the relevant main wind directions for a specific site and time with high accuracy due to the inherent uncertainty of wind direction information taken from local measurements or weather prediction models and because of the nonstationarity of atmospheric flows. However, performing simulations with a sampling rate of 1° or less is not realizable due to the high computing costs that would be associated with it. In this study, we therefore identify how small changes of the wind direction around a reference value affect the turbulent and mean wind quantities. We run two additional simulations (N3e⁻ and N3e⁺) that only differ in their geostrophic wind direction by $\pm 5^\circ$ from the reference case (N3e). The results in Fig. 8, which displays vertical profiles of v_d

Fig. 8. Profiles of the magnitude of the horizontally and temporally averaged horizontal wind vector (left) and TKE (right) for three different geostrophic wind directions (blue: 85° , black: 90° , green: 95°) at the end of the simulation (neutral case with 3 m s^{-1} geostrophic wind). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

and TKE for various wind directions, suggest that both wind speed and TKE are not significantly affected by changing the direction by $\pm 5^\circ$. The discrepancies to the reference case with 90° are marginal compared to the actual magnitude of the regarded quantity (mostly less than 1%). Also, the investigation of local differences between horizontal cross sections reveals this behavior (not shown). Therefore, we state that simulations for a specific wind direction can be regarded as representative for a complete wind sector of at least 10° so that a maximum of 36 runs would be sufficient to take care for all possible wind directions.

Finally, our findings demonstrate that for each given magnitude and direction of the geostrophic wind, the spatial variability of the wind speed and TKE within the city is less pronounced in case of surface heating compared to the neutral situation (not shown). This matches the observation described above, that local wind field differences caused by a change in wind direction are generally more distinct in neutrally stratified atmospheres than under unstable stratifications. In other words, the local effects of the buildings' distribution on the wind are weaker under convection, which is often the daytime condition. This is a direct consequence of the enhanced mixing, which is associated with the surface heating. Note, the horizontal homogeneity of the heating limits the spatial variability of the turbulent wind field under convection. In real conditions, much larger horizontal variations might appear, for example, between the built-up city area and the surrounding sea in Kowloon.

3.3. Virtual flights

For safe drone operations, the turbulent wind information must be known in advance to decide if a flight can be carried out or not. This is especially true along planned flight paths. To decide which route is appropriate under which meteorological conditions, LES in general can provide relevant data. PALM in particular has a built-in virtual flight module, which can be used to sample such data along

flight paths during the simulation (Schröter et al., 2000; Sühring and Raasch, 2013). A virtual point sensor is moving through the four-dimensional (space and time), turbulent wind field and measures with a sampling rate given by the time step of the model. Note, compared to real flight experiments, measurements are not affected by the sensor inertia or turbulent movements of the aircraft. By default, the flight measurements capture the information of all three velocity components through linear interpolation from the grid points to the actual location of the sensor.

Fig. 9 shows the sensor's time series of a single flight, which has been performed during NC. The whole flight (see Fig. 9a) lasts about 26 min (from 14400 to 15937 s simulated time) with a ground speed of 2 m s^{-1} . It is a straight, one-way flight that starts at the roof top of vertiport 1 in child 1 (at 38 m altitude), crosses the parent domain, and ends at the roof top of vertiport 4 in child 2 (at 126 m altitude). Because of the different heights of the start and end point, a constant climb/descent of $\pm 0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ is assumed (triangular vertical profile of the trajectory), which results in a maximum flight altitude of 466 m after approximately 14 min (15250 s simulated time). The velocity information is taken from the respective model instance, where the sensor is located, i.e., as soon as the sensor is within a child domain, the child solution is taken, otherwise the parent solution. The time series of u , v , and w show fluctuations of more than 1 m s^{-1} within time intervals of about 10 s. Once the sensor is located far away from the densely built-up areas, wind fluctuations (rates of change) are smaller. This is especially visible from the end of the flight within child 1 (~ 14600 s) until the beginning of the flight within child 2 (~ 15700 s). In addition, the general level of the rate of change in wind speed is higher in the child domains than in the parent because of the higher grid resolution, which also resolves smaller-scale fluctuations from the inertial subrange of the energy spectrum (Bull and Jameson, 2016; Spiga et al., 2016). A flying virtual drone experiences this through higher-frequency turbulence, which becomes more obvious in the enlarged time series (see Fig. 9b), showing the transition from child 1 to the parent domain. These time

Fig. 9. Virtual flight measurements of the velocity components (a and b). The vertical solid lines indicate the simulation times at which the flight sensor enters another domain. The dashed lines show the start and end time of the enlarged time series presented in b. At the bottom (c), the flight altitude is shown.

series also indicate the previously described lower turbulence at around 14600 s compared to the beginning of the performed flight leg due to the decreasing building influence on the flow (the drone climbs and gradually leaves the urban environment). A principle difference among the three components cannot be observed. Only a tendency to negative u -values is noted, which is caused by the geostrophic wind from the east.

Because the virtual flight introduced in this section only shows 1D samples over a limited distance and at a certain point in time, the statistical significance of the results is limited. If the flight had been carried out only several minutes later, it would have shown completely different turbulent signals. To take this into account, several statistically independent flights could be performed during the same simulation. If affordable, a simulation ensemble, consisting of several statistically independent realizations of the same flight could also be generated (Sühling and Raasch, 2013). However, the single flight presented in Fig. 9 serves as a good demonstration of how statistical quantities, like maximum/minimum occurring absolute/relative fluctuations, the mean, or standard deviations can be derived from LES data along a certain flight path. Also more advanced quantities than the pure velocities, which have a direct effect on the drone flight path, can be extracted, for example, the wind shear along certain directions to calculate roll, pitch, and gear moments.

Eventually, there is the possibility to couple LES with flight simulators to consider the effects of the turbulent wind field on the flight path and attitude. Possible open source flight simulators for this purpose are FlightGear (Perry, 2004), which focuses on the civilian air traffic and flight experiences of single planes, and BlueSky (Hoekstra and

Ellerbroek, 2016), which is especially designed for the research on air traffic management and air traffic flows for any kind of aircraft. A coupling enables, for example, the opportunity to assess the risk of collision between aircraft that are flying within turbulent winds or the danger of an accident during critical flight operations like the landing or departure phase. However, to do this realistically, the simulation of the wind should be able to resolve the most relevant turbulent scales for the considered aircraft and the flight simulator must be able to process 3D turbulent wind data in its flight dynamics model. BlueSky, for example, is only able to handle horizontal wind information at the drone's location. A further challenging task to realize the coupling is the efficient and meaningful integration of the 3D time-dependent wind field data into the flight simulator. Our experiences show that it is currently not possible to use all the simulated wind fields at every time step due to huge amount of data that must be loaded. Either one snapshot of the wind field could be incorporated in the flight simulator, which requires the assumption of the so-called Taylor or frozen turbulence hypothesis, or different snapshots at certain points in time could be used, which requires interpolation between the selected times and much more data that need to be loaded. Otherwise, the performance decrease of the flight simulator would make it unusable for most of the practical purposes.

3.4. Computational costs and potential savings

The large increase in computing power over the last decades has meanwhile allowed LES to be used for industrial purposes with acceptable costs. Table 2 shows an overview of the setup features (domain

Table 2
Computational resources.

Simulation name	Domain size $L_x \times L_y \times L_z$ (m ³)	Number of grid points	Grid spacing (m)	CPU cores	Wall-clock time (h)	Cost price (€)
Np	6000 × 9000 × 2345	600 × 900 × 102	10	1500		
Nc1	1040 × 1040 × 521	520 × 520 × 262	2	1690		
Ns		~ 1.26 × 10 ⁸		3190	27	3405
Cp	6000 × 9000 × 2345	600 × 900 × 102	10	1500		
Cc1	1040 × 1040 × 521	520 × 520 × 262	2	1690		
Cc2	1040 × 1040 × 521	520 × 520 × 262	2	1690		
Cs		~ 1.97 × 10 ⁸		4880	17	3160
N3e	1024 × 1024 × 1885	512 × 512 × 290	2	1024	23	915

size, grid spacing, number of grid points) of some of our simulations and the respective resources that have been used in terms of the number of CPU cores and wall-clock times. The cost price is also given based on the schedule of fees of the North-German Supercomputing Alliance (as of 2020, see <https://www.hlrn.de>) that industrial users would be charged. The lower-case letter “s” at the end of the simulation name reflects the sum of all domains. Wall-clock times and cost prices are only specified for the whole run. Even the nested simulations do not cost more than a few thousand euros. However, the wall-clock times are more than an order of magnitude above what a daily operational forecast would allow for. Furthermore, spending a few thousand euros each day for a drone weather forecast for each single city would not be acceptable. A suitable way to overcome these problems is to run a set of simulations for relevant wind speeds, wind directions, and atmospheric stratifications in advance of the drone operations and to store results in a data base, as discussed in Section 2.

There are several options to further reduce the computational costs, which we will shortly discuss now. Concerning a single run, main parameters that affect the computing costs are the domain size and the spatial resolution. Both together determine the total number of grid points. Therefore, the nested run with unstable stratification and with two children (NC) is the most expensive one. However, the neutrally stratified nested case with one child (Ns) shows the highest value in terms of the cost price because convection significantly reduces the required time to be simulated in order to get converged statistics, which is why Cs is stopped about 10 h earlier than Ns (see wall-clock time in Table 2). Unfortunately, reducing the resolution in the child domains to save some costs is not appropriate here. Our experiences suggest that a grid spacing well above 2 m is, at least in urban environments, too coarse for the regions of interest to which, in particular, the vertiports belong. Also, a reduced resolution in the parent domain is not recommended. As indicated by Hellsten et al. (2021), a grid spacing ratio between parent and child of more than 5 should be avoided in any case. A significant shortening of the simulated time, however, would be possible, since we have used averaging intervals much longer than averaging periods applied so far in other LES studies (e.g., Wurps et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021; Tuerke and Jiménez, 2013; Zhou et al., 2020). The reason was to reduce the statistical uncertainty of single runs to a minimum in order to allow for comparisons between different runs, for example, to identify how turbulence quantities depend on the wind direction. Under most circumstances, simulations do not require to run for more than a few large-eddy turnover times. In this way, our runs could be shortened from 65 h to 25 h for the neutral stratification, and from 14 h to 5 h for the convective case.

Another significant way to spare resources would be to omit the nesting and to limit the computational domain to the surroundings of the vertiports because only here turbulent wind fluctuations may critically affect the UAM operation. Furthermore, turbulence is hardly influenced by local building effects at cruising levels of UAM aircraft. For drone operations that take place within the urban canopy layer, simulations could be limited to the respective city district. However, without the nesting the simulation has the general problem of how to get turbulence information at the lateral boundaries. Any turbulence

that is generated, for example, by buildings outside of the domain, and that shall be transported through the lateral boundaries into the domain cannot be accounted for. Instead, synthetic turbulence could be added at the boundaries (Kim et al., 2013), but this does not represent the real conditions. One frequently applied solution is to use cyclic lateral boundary conditions, to add buffer zones around the area of interest, and to restrict the data analysis to those parts of the domain which are not affected by the inappropriate cyclic conditions (Letzel et al., 2012). The buffer zones allow the turbulent wind field to adjust to the forcing by the local buildings.

Fig. 10 shows horizontal cross sections of the temporally averaged TKE and horizontal wind vectors at a height of 45 m for the nested run Nc1 (top) and N3e with cyclic boundary conditions (bottom). Due to the given geostrophic wind of 3 m s⁻¹ from the east, large differences appear between the two runs at the northern and eastern inflow boundary, but results converge with increasing distance from these boundaries. Differences appear to be significantly reduced, qualitatively as well as quantitatively, in the southwestern part of the domain, where the three vertiports are located. These differences could be further reduced by enlarging the domain size. In order to account for any background wind direction, the area of interest, that is the vertiport locations, should be placed in the center of the domain. Using a non-nested, high-resolution simulation that is restricted to the vertiport locations reduces the costs in our case by a factor of 4 (see Ns and N3e in Table 2).

4. Conclusions

In this study, we demonstrated and discussed strategies for turbulence-resolving atmospheric flow simulations to assess meteorological conditions for safe drone operations in urban environments. A literature review revealed that no regulations or frameworks exist that address this issue in a sophisticated manner, although more and more small aerial vehicles are operating in and around cities. Depending on their morphology, buildings can significantly modify the local atmospheric turbulence. However, this study highlights that turbulence measures and their thresholds that may be qualified to guarantee safe drone operations under turbulent wind conditions are still unknown. Due to this knowledge lack, we introduced and discussed possible measures which have already been used in the past for characterizing turbulence and which have also been partly used in aviation.

The numerical simulations were performed with the high-resolution state-of-the-art LES model PALM for Hong Kong, Kowloon, as an example for a highly developed, densely populated area. Using LES for assessment studies needs to take into account the computational resources required for these kinds of simulations. Although PALM is a highly optimized model, wall-clock times are in the order of ten hours, which is not very expensive from a cost perspective, but does not allow to run it for operational forecasts on a daily basis. Instead, we suggest to generate a meteorological data base well in advance of the drone operation, where site-specific synoptic situations are categorized into a limited number of scenarios. From this data base, relevant information can be extracted based on the current synoptic weather situation or weather forecast and the drone operation scenario.

Fig. 10. Horizontal cross sections of the temporally averaged TKE and horizontal wind vector at a height of 45 m for the nested (a) and non-nested (b) setup (neutral case). The gray dots denote the locations of the vertiports. Buildings are displayed in black.

For the generation of such a data base, it is still necessary to decrease the computational demands and to reduce the number of required scenarios to a minimum. Parameters like the resolution, the total domain size or the simulation and averaging times must be carefully chosen. Our sensitivity study for the wind direction has shown, that results from a simulation with a given direction α can be taken as representative for a sector of at least $\alpha \pm 5^\circ$ so that a maximum of 36 runs may cover all possible wind directions. As the typical daytime unstable stratification strongly enhances the turbulence level, the simulated scenarios must also consider some neutrally and unstably stratified atmospheric conditions. Stable stratification is regarded as not crucial, because it normally comes along with weak wind situations and suppresses the generation of turbulence. Like in previous studies, we found that the local effect of buildings on turbulence is significantly weakened for unstable stratification, which limits possible dangers of specific building configurations to drones.

Another option to reduce computational demands is to use nesting features of a numerical model, which allow to limit high spatial resolution to the surroundings of vertiports, where in particular the small-scale wind fluctuations may critically affect the drone operation. Lower resolution can then be used for the outermost nest because

drones are less sensitive to turbulent winds at cruising levels and no local small-scale wind effects of buildings appear at these heights. In a further step, simulations could just be restricted to the local environment of vertiports. The technical problem of providing turbulence information at the inflow boundary of LES models can be circumvented by using cyclic lateral boundary conditions and an additional buffer zone. In this way, we were able to reduce the computational costs by a factor of 4 compared to a nested setup.

The computational effort for calculating turbulence measures needs to be taken into account, too, especially if area-wide information is desired for a model domain with high grid resolution. Measures that can be calculated during the simulation based on the available data in the memory of the machine can easily be provided for all model grid points without any significant computational costs. This even holds for variances that require temporal averaging because of the spatial heterogeneity of the mean flow. As we have shown, they can be calculated for each grid point by introducing additional 3D arrays for summation and using the Reynolds decomposition and Reynolds averaging rules. Other quantities like the energy dissipation rate require to output time-dependent data (i.e., for each time step and grid point) to hard disk in order to calculate the energy spectra in a post-processing step. This increases the computational time for the LES and the post-processing by orders of magnitude and data may not fit even on the biggest disks. Therefore, such quantities should only be considered for studying conditions at specific locations inside the model domain. In order to avoid the need to carry out runs for different mean background wind speeds, a quantity normalized by the mean wind, like the turbulence intensity, is of advantage. However, the independence of the turbulence intensity on the mean wind has only been shown for horizontally homogeneous surfaces and is violated for low wind speeds. While the latter restriction is probably less important for evaluating drone operations, the behavior of turbulence intensity for complex terrain like urban environments requires further investigations.

In addition to provide area-wide turbulence information, we used our LES for virtual flights, which were performed online during the wind field simulations. They are a useful tool to investigate the meteorological hazard along specific flight paths because they exactly provide the turbulent wind information that a drone experiences during its operation. It is, however, necessary to generate several independent realizations of the same flight to have an ensemble, which can then be statistically investigated. One virtual flight over a limited distance and at a certain point in time may give only limited information about the turbulent flow along a certain route.

Data from such virtual flights or highly resolved LES turbulent wind field data in general can also be used as input to flight dynamic models and flight simulators like FlightGear (Perry, 2004) or BlueSky (Hoekstra and Ellerbroek, 2016), as recently done for flight load assessment near wind farms (Varriale et al., 2018). Urban turbulent wind fields from PALM are currently used as input to BlueSky within the *U-space Separation in Europe (USEPE)* project funded by the European Union (see section Funding Sources).

Beside the generic meteorological setups that have been used in our study, real case scenarios should also be addressed in the future. The PALM model system already provides a mesoscale nesting interface, which allows to import data from larger-scale weather forecast models as boundary conditions (Kadasch et al., 2021). Therefore, non-stationary synoptic conditions can be taken into account. The various surface models that are integrated in PALM allow to consider flow features that are generated by heterogeneous surfaces, like land-sea-breeze circulations that occur for Kowloon peninsula. Furthermore, the 3D radiation model that is integrated in PALM (Krc et al., 2021) is able to calculate the net radiation for building surfaces, including shadow effects, and this radiation can be used as input for a surface energy balance model to calculate the building wall surface temperatures. LES models will be a valuable tool to study these kind of effects and, of course, for the general assessment of safe drone operation conditions in urban environments.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sebastian Giersch: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Omar El Guernaoui:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources. **Siegfried Raasch:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Manuela Sauer:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Marta Palomar:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data are accessible via <https://doi.org/10.25835/727jszhs> or available on request.

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